

Table 2 continued.

Treatment	Mean	Genotypic variance	Genotypic coefficient of variation (%)	Heritability (broad sense) percentage	Genetic advance (% of mean)
<i>Panicle length (cm)</i>					
Control	26.35	0	0	0	0
4 h	25.13	0.047	0.8	7.5	0.48
6 h	22.88	0.355	2.6	22.9	2.56
8 h	22.41	0.877	4.1	28.1	4.55
<i>Filled grains (no./panicle)</i>					
Control	160.38	0	0	0	0
4 h	146.94	10.970	2.2	15.7	1.83
6 h	129.72	23.833	3.7	21.9	3.62
8 h	126.16	24.435	3.9	22.1	3.78
<i>Weight of 1000 grains (g)</i>					
Control	19.16	0	0	0	0
4 h	19.32	0.006	0.4	3.0	0.14
6 h	19.53	0.016	0.6	7.1	0.35
8 h	19.58	0.018	0.6	7.8	0.39
<i>Yield per plant (g)</i>					
Control	24.62	0	0	0	0
4 h	22.97	0.724	3.7	13.6	2.81
6 h	22.31	1.340	5.1	18.6	4.59
8 h	22.01	2.145	6.6	22.3	6.46

EMS treatment induced genetic variability and genetic advance in the five quantitative traits. The longer the treatment, the higher the estimated genetic parameter. EMS treatment could be used to select improved plant types on the basis of induced polygenic variability, particularly in the M_3 .

ERRATUM

IRRN 11:3 (Jun 1986) p. 25. On the item titled *Efficacy of slow-release N fertilizers on rice in coastal soils of Karnataka*, the author list was garbled. It should read: A.M. Krishnappa, K. Kenchaiah, B.N. Patil, Badrinath, K. Balakrishna Rao, and N.A. Janardhana Gowda. Mr. Badrinath's name was omitted.

Improved White Ponni released in Tamil Nadu

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Improved White Ponni has been released as a new variety for Tamil Nadu. It yields 300 kg/ha more than the local White Ponni but resembles it in all other characteristics.

Improved White Ponni, with 135-140 d maturity, is suitable for Sep-Oct and Jan-Feb plantings. At 130-135 cm tall, it is prone to lodging. Maximum yield was 6.3 t/ha. In 1984 data from 170 places in 11 districts, Improved White Ponni outyielded IR20 in 8 districts with an average 4.2 t/ha, 5.8% more than IR20 (Table 1). Average yield of

Improved White Ponni is 4.5 t/ha. Maximum yield potential is 9.2 t/ha. Improved White Ponni gives a straw yield of 7.4 t/ha (moisture-free basis)

compared to 4.5 t/ha for IR20 and 5.0 t/ha for CO 43.

The improved variety is moderately resistant to tungro (RTV), leaf

Table 1. Performance of Improved White Ponni in farmers' fields. Tamil Nadu, India.

District	Locations (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	
		Improved White Ponni	IR20
Thanjavur	39	3.3	2.2
Trichirappalli	7	5.8	4.6
Pudukkottai	8	3.9	3.6
Madurai	10	3.6	4.0
Ramanathapuram	2	3.0	3.7
Tirunelveli	24	4.1	2.9
Kanyakumari	4	4.1	4.0
Coimbatore	16	5.4	5.9
Salem	32	4.8	4.9
Dharmapuri	3	4.8	4.1
Chingleput	25	3.8	3.7
Total	170		
Mean		4.2	3.9

Table 2. Reaction^a of Improved White Ponni to diseases and insects. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	RTV		Leaf yellowing (field)	B1		BB (field)	Sheath rot (field)	Grain discoloration (field)	Leaffolder (field)	Mite (field)	GLH (inoculated)
	Field	Inoculated		Field	Inoculated						
Improved White Ponni	3 (R)	5 (MR)	3-5 (MR)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)	3-5 (MR)	3 (R)	3 (R)	5-7 (MS)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)
IR20	8 (S)	9 (S)	7 (S)	7 (MS)	5-7 (MS)	3-5 (MR)	3 (R)	3 (R)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)
CO 43	7 (S)	8 (S)	7 (S)	3 (R)	5 (MR)	3-5 (MR)	5-7 (MS)	5 (MS)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)	-

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

yellowing, blast (Bl), and bacterial blight (BB), and resistant to grain discoloration in farmers' fields. Under artificial inoculation, it was moderately resistant to RTV and Bl. In 1984, when

all other medium-duration varieties succumbed to an epidemic outbreak of leaf yellowing, Improved White Ponni tolerated the stress throughout Tamil Nadu. It is moderately resistant to mite

and green leafhopper (GLH), the vector for transmitting RTV (Table 2).

Cooking quality is very good, protein content is 9.88%. *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

No first internode found in Nepalese varieties

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Four groups of Nepalese local cultivars were measured for internode elongation at maturity. Group 1 consisted of 15 local rice varieties that are tall, photoperiod insensitive, and mature within 110 d. Group 2 consisted of seven Gamadi-type local varieties in which the panicle does not exert from heading to maturity but remains enclosed in the flag leaf sheath. Other names for the Gamadi-type are Garvey, Dulhaniya, Kaniya, Thagiya, Sathi, and Satha. These varieties are dwarf type and mature within 100 d. Group 3 consisted of 36 local upland rice cultivars that are tall and mature in 100-110 d. Group 4 consisted of 20 local cultivars that are tall and photoperiod sensitive.

Direct seeding of groups 1, 2, and 3 was on 7 Apr and of group 4 on 15 Jun 1985 in the main plot under normal cultural conditions. Ten main culms were randomly sampled from 10 plants of each variety and culm length, panicle length, and length of each elongated upper internode measured.

All groups except group 2 showed normal elongation of the upper internodes, although total culm length varied significantly (see figure). In group 2, the first internode from the top was absent but the rest of the upper internodes showed normal elongation. This absence of the first internode from the top coincided with panicle enclosure within the flag leaf sheath and is important in the evolution of rice from the wild stage to cultivation. *S*

Elongation (cm)

Internode elongation of Nepalese local germlasm.

Screening for dormancy in 39 rice varieties

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The 39 varieties screened had these maturity characteristics: 2 early maturing aus, photoperiod insensitive, 90-100 d maturity; 16 early maturing aman, photoperiod sensitive, 140-148 d; 12 medium maturing aman,

photoperiod sensitive, 160-165 d, and 9 medium-late and late maturing aman, photoperiod sensitive, more than 165 d.

Seeds for three replications were thoroughly dried in the sun, cleaned, and kept in the laboratory in thin cloth bags at room temperature. Germination tests were started 10 d after harvest at regular intervals until dormancy was completely broken.

Seeds were germinated in petri dishes on moist blotting paper for 6 d. When